

Derivation of Shannon's Entropy for Constraints Sum over i $f(e_i)$ with Probability $P(e_i)$

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In (1), it is suggested that there are two fundamental approaches to obtaining a probability distribution. The first, called the principle of indifference, is associated with a uniform distribution as in the toss of a coin or die. If a constraint on probabilities is present, however, then there is bias and (1) suggests that Shannon's entropy $-\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ be maximized subject to the constraint.

In (2), we argued that for a constraint associated with a conserved quantity, i.e. $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$, one may take a subset of $p(e_i)$ s ($0 \leq e_i \leq E_1$) and apply the notion of a uniform distribution to $p(e_i)p(e_j)$ in this subset without any other constraint. Then one immediately has a solution from $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i+e_j)$, i.e. $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ for a probability which drops with rising e_i .

Here we argue that one may extend this idea to a constraint of the form $\sum_i f(e_i)$ as this may be rewritten in terms of conserved quantity, i.e. $\sum_i f(e_i)/P(e_i) P(e_i)$ with $g(e_i) = f(e_i)/P(e_i)$ being seen as the conserved quantity. In such a case, one may write $P(e_i)$ as $P_1(g(e_i))$ and use $P_1(g(e_i)) P_1(g(e_j)) = P_1(g(e_i)+g(e_j))$. Then the solution is $P_1(g(e_i)) = \exp(-g(e_i)/T)$ or $\ln(P_1(g(e_i))) = g(e_i)$.

The above ideas may then be applied to the full $P(e_i)$ set because one may argue that one seeks a special function $F(P(e_i))$ which is maximized under $P(e_i) \rightarrow P(e_i) + dP(e_i)$ subject to the constraint. This means that $dF/dP_1 = g(e_i)$ from the subset uniform product probability reasoning. Thus, $F = -\sum_i P_1(g(e_i)) \ln(P_1(g(e_i)))$. Now $P_1(g(e_i)) = P(e_i)$ so $F = -\sum_i P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i))$ and so we argue that Shannon's entropy arises in such a manner.

In other words, for a constraint of the form $\sum_i f(e_i) = \text{number}$, there is one fundamental idea, namely that of a uniform distribution. The notion of Shannon's entropy and its maximization subject to a constraint follow from the uniform distribution on a subset of $P(e_i)$ s when one focuses on $P(e_i)P(e_j)$.

Two Principles for Determining a Probability $P(e_i)$

In (1), it is suggested that there are two general math approaches to finding probability. The first is called the principle of indifference and is associated with a uniform distribution as in the toss of a coin or die. In particular, there is no bias in such a scenario. If, however, there exists a constraint in $P(e_i)$'s, then there is a bias and a uniform distribution no longer holds. In such a case, (1) suggests that one should create Shannon's entropy $-\sum_i P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i))$ and maximize it subject to the constraint. We suggest for constraints of the form $\sum_i f(e_i) = \text{number}$ (where f is an arbitrary function), that one may create a conserved quantity $g(e_i)$ and apply a uniform distribution to a $P(e_i)P(e_j)$ for a subset of $P(e_i)$'s. In other words, Shannon's entropy and its maximization subject to a constraint on all $P(e_i)$'s follow from the uniform distribution applied to a subset of $P(e_i)$ s through the product probability $P(e_i)P(e_j)$ being uniform for all $e_i+e_j=E_1$. (E_1 may then be changed to take on different values.)

Conservation of e_i

In (2), we argued that if one has the constraint $\sum_i e_i P(e_i) = E_{ave}$, one may use the notion of conservation of e_i . In particular, one may consider an E_1 and two body elastic interactions such that $P(e_i)P(e_j) = P(e_k)P(e_l)$ if $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l = E_1$. This is equivalent to $P(e_i)P(e_j) = P(e_i + e_j)$ so $P(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ to have $P(e_i)$ drop with rising e_i . In such a case, one works with a subset of $P(e_i)$ s, i.e. only ones associated with $0 \leq e_i \leq E_1$. Within this subset, the product $P(e_i)P(e_j)$ is uniform as there is no global constraint on this product probability.

In this special case, $C \exp(-e_i/T)$ is already known without maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to the constraint $\sum_i e_i P(e_i)$. There is, however, nothing wrong with maximizing Shannon's entropy because from the subset uniform distribution one knows that:

$$\ln(P(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad (\text{form } P(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((1))$$

If one argues that one seeks a function $F(P(e_i))$ which is maximized under $P(e_i) \rightarrow P(e_i) + dP(e_i)$ subject to the constraint $\sum_i e_i P(e_i)$, then one knows that:

$$dF/dP = -e_i/T = \ln(P(e_i)) + \text{constant} \quad ((2))$$

Note: One may add a constant to $\ln(P(e_i))$ which becomes part of the normalization constant.

Thus, F is automatically Shannon's entropy:

$$S = - \sum_i P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i)) \quad ((3))$$

We wish to generalize this idea to constraints of the form $\sum_i f(e_i) = \text{number}$, where $f(e_i)$ is an arbitrary function.

Constraints of the Form $\sum_i f(e_i) = \text{number}$

Given a constraint of the form $\sum_i f(e_i) = \text{number}$, we argue that one may write it in terms of a conserved quantity:

$$\sum_i f(e_i) = \sum_i \{ f(e_i)/P(e_i) \} P(e_i) \quad \text{because } P(e_i) > 0 \quad ((4))$$

$g(e_i) = f(e_i)/P(e_i)$ is the conserved quantity and:

$$P_1(g(e_i)) = P(e_i) \quad ((5))$$

One may use the subset of $P(e_i)$'s approach together with the uniform distribution, i.e.

$$P_1(g(e_i)) P_1(g(e_j)) = P_1(g(e_i) + g(e_j)) \quad \text{so } P_1(g(e_i)) = C \exp(-g(e_i)/T) \quad ((6)) \quad \text{or}$$

$$\ln(P_1(g(e_i))) = -g(e_i)/T \quad ((7))$$

If one moves out of the subset of $P(e_i)$'s to the full set of $P(e_i)$'s and the full constraint $\sum_i f(e_i) = \text{number}$, one may imagine a function $F(P_1(e_i))$ which may be maximized subject to the constraint to produce the probability distribution, i.e.

$$dF/dP_1 = -g(e_i)/T + \text{constant} \quad ((8))$$

One may add the constant because it becomes part of the normalization constant. Then:

$$F = - \sum_i P_1(g(e_i)) \ln(P_1(g(e_i))) \quad ((9))$$

Now $P_1(g(e_i)) = P(e_i)$ so

$$F = - \sum_i P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i)) \quad ((10))$$

Thus, one obtains the Shannon's entropy form and its maximization with respect to the full constraint $\sum_i f(e_i) = \text{number}$ from considerations of a uniform distribution $P_1(g(e_i))P_1(g(e_j))$ on a subject of $P(e_i)$ s in general.

As a result, for constraint of the form $\sum_i f(e_i)$, maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to a constraint is not a process which is independent of the uniform distribution, i.e. principle of indifference, we argue

Conclusion

In conclusion, in (1) it is suggested that there are two general mathematical principles for obtaining probability distributions. The first, called the principle of indifference, is based on the uniform distribution as there is no bias and applies to tosses of coins and dice. If a constraint on $P(e_i)$'s (probabilities) exists, then there is a bias and (1) suggests that one maximize Shannon's entropy $-\sum_i P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i))$ subject to the constraint. We argue that a constraint of the form $\sum_i f(e_i) = \text{number}$, may always be written in terms of a conserved quantity, i.e. $\sum_i \{f(e_i)/P(e_i)\} P(e_i)$ with $g(e_i) = \text{conserved quantity}$. One may then write $P_1(g(e_i)) = P(e_i)$ and consider a subject of $P_1(e_i)$ s with $g(e_i) + g(e_j) = E_1$ such that $P_1(g(e_i))P_1(g(e_j)) = P_1(g(e_i) + g(e_j))$ or $P(e_i) = C \exp(-g(e_i)/T)$. Thus, one only needs the concept of a uniform distribution in such a case, and not the notion of Shannon's entropy and its maximization subject to a constraint.

One may, however, derive Shannon's entropy and its maximization from the subset-uniform distribution approach based on the result $\ln(P_1(g(e_i))) = -g(e_i)/T$. If one suggests that there is a function $F(P_1(e_i))$ which may be maximized subject to the constraint $\sum_i f(e_i)$, then $dF/dP_1 = -g(e_i)/T = \ln(P_1(g(e_i))) + \text{constant}$, with the $\ln(P_1(e_i))$ following from the subset solution. Then $F = - \sum_i P_1(g(e_i)) \ln(P_1(g(e_i)))$, but $P_1(g(e_i)) = P(e_i)$ so $F = \text{Shannon's entropy} = - \sum_i P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i))$. Thus, the maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to constraints is not a concept independent of the uniform distribution result for constraints of the form $\sum_i f(e_i) = \text{number}$.

References

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